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No room in the North: housing scarcity as infrastructure's failed relations in the Arctic

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the entanglements of housing infrastructure, economic structures, and social relations in Arctic regions, focusing on Nunavut (Canada) and Malmfälten (Sweden). Using a comparative ethnographic approach, we explore how housing scarcity is shaped not only by physical infrastructure but by broader political and economic forces. Drawing on thematic content analysis and an infrastructural relations framework, we highlight how capitalist logics, demographic shifts, and governance structures contribute to ongoing housing crises. Rather than viewing infrastructure as a static entity, we adopt a relational perspective that emphasizes the reciprocal dynamics between housing, social networks, and state policies. Our findings suggest that housing scarcity in the Arctic is not merely a consequence of remoteness or material limitations but a product of structural neglect, economic disincentives, and governance complexities. By framing infrastructure as a site of contested relations rather than a neutral technical system, we argue that addressing Arctic housing challenges requires not only increased investment but a fundamental rethinking of infrastructural governance, social responsibility, and sustainability in northern communities.

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Introduction

The Arctic is often imagined as a vast wilderness of vast empty spaces stretching over long distances (e.g. Cooke, 2016), yet it is also home to human communities and built infrastructure, where the abundance of space paradoxically coexists with a shortage of housing. Restricted construction space in the Arctic is not only a matter of geography but also one of financing profitability. Investments in housing are often deprioritized, viewed as economically unviable due to perceived risks, high costs of construction and repair, low or declining population numbers, and the transient nature of many extractive industries (Avango et al., 2022; Klinger et al., 2023; Malmgren et al., 2022). Furthermore, national political and organizational complications frequently hinder development, creating a mismatch between infrastructure availability and the willingness to build homes (Sandström, 2023).

In this article we explore these contradictions, focusing on the overlooked perspectives of Arctic residents to shed light on the broader structural and economic forces that contribute

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to housing scarcity across distinct contexts. We categorize ‘housing’ as a type of infrastructure which is dependent on and shapes relations. In doing so, we expand the understanding of infrastructure beyond that of the built environment, choosing instead to examine housing’s role in reciprocal social-relational networks (Ingold, 2000; 2021). Specifically, we explore how Arctic infrastructures influence the wellbeing and everyday lives of local residents. We address the research question: *What effects do limited housing options have on local residents in the communities of Malmfälten and Nunavut?*

The topic of Arctic housing is explored in academic literature through various interdisciplinary lenses. Some studies focus on place-based amenities (Howe & Huskey, 2022), while others examine housing histories from demographic perspectives (Heleniak, 2025a; 2025b). Additional research investigates the role of housing in attracting and retaining residents in rural regions (Kelly & Eimermann, 2024), while others adopt an architectural perspective, exploring the concept of smart Arctic cities (Rizzo et al., 2023). Anthropologists, on the other hand, often examine people’s attitudes toward their homes (Nakhshina, 2013) or perspectives on home and household (Anderson et al., 2013). From a broader built environment perspective, Schweitzer (2017) discuss the ‘right of remoteness’, Gartler et al. (2025) examine infrastructural challenges in permafrost regions, while Eriksen (2022) highlights the unintended consequences of infrastructure, emphasizing the intrinsic connection between physical structures and social relations – an issue we underscore in this article.

However, we identified a significant gap in the existing literature on Arctic housing infrastructures: (1) the lack of comparative analyses that prioritize local residents’ perspectives and (2) a relational perspective to understand the entanglements of housing infrastructures. Such an approach not only enriches the existing discourse by incorporating lived experiences but also provides insights into why housing remains a scarce resource in distinct Arctic contexts. Adding a comparative lens to our analysis allows us to concentrate on structural commonalities and differences across our case studies rather than running the risk of ‘explaining away’ contextual reasons for local housing shortages. We follow Appel et al. (2018) and Ferguson (2012) in their assertion that ethnographic studies of infrastructure are well suited to illuminate questions of materiality and sociality, shedding light on essential infrastructures and the built environment as fundamental components of the social worlds people inhabit. These worlds are shaped by colonialism (Bernauer, 2019; Tester & Kulchyski, 1994), post- and green colonialism (Sandström, 2024), gender (Quintal-Marineau & Wenzel, 2019), race (Smith, 2025), and economic and political decisions (Dahl et al., 2000; Damas, 2002), which influence not only who has access to housing but also *how*, *where*, and *when* new housing is built.

Despite the presence of infrastructure to support construction, there is a lack of incentive to invest in these communities. This stems from risks associated with declining population numbers, the absence of a housing market, and/or the rather short-term (from a housing investment perspective) nature of extractive industries. Consequently, we argue that housing scarcity in the Arctic is not solely a matter of infrastructure availability. Rather, the challenges are rooted in broader economic and structural dynamics. We demonstrate, how housing infrastructures are embedded in networks of social, economic, and institutional relations. This perspective allows us to move beyond market-based explanations without dismissing them, and to foreground the ways in which housing is shaped by – and simultaneously shapes – interactions between actors, policies, and place-based conditions.

In the following, we begin by situating our understandings of housing as a relational infrastructure within broader theoretical debates before introducing our case study

regions and methodological approach. In our empirical section, we combine examples from our field sites to illustrate the magnitude of the northern housing crisis, and the dependency of northern residents on functioning funding schemes, social-oriented governance, and local social networks, to receive and maintain their housing. We examine the relationship between the Arctic climate, climate change, and northern housing, before continuing our analysis along four categories, which we used to guide our inquiry and comparison: funding and governance, population dynamics, infrastructure and logistics, and suitability of housing in the North. In our concluding discussion we highlight how housing scarcity in the Arctic stems less from remoteness than from structural neglect, economic disincentives, and governance challenges.

Theorizing housing infrastructure's failed relations

Examining the Arctic from the perspective of the 'built environment' illuminates human-induced transformations in the North. Two key perspectives shape this analysis: the 'building perspective' and the 'dwelling perspective' (Heidegger, 1971; Ingold, 2000). The building perspective views the built environment as a collection of finished products surrounding the subject, while the dwelling perspective emphasizes ongoing processes of making, building and inhabiting, embedding the subject within a dynamic network of material relations. Building on the foundation of relational theories in social anthropology by Ingold (2017; 2021) we find it useful to apply this perspective to our case studies on Arctic housing, as our empirical data reveals a variety of relational entanglements. Ingold (2021) suggests that when people appreciate objects as part of their personal or collective histories, they form relations with them. This perspective extends to housing, as the relations people develop with their homes and housing conditions are deeply significant in their individual life-courses. Moffatt and Kohler (2008) stress the need to understand the built environment in its historical context, considering both contemporary conceptions of 'the environment', and the shifting meanings and uses of built structures over time.

Infrastructure, as part of the built environment, navigates the temporalities of becoming, breakdown, and repair throughout its 'lifetime' (Gupta, 2018), shaping and being shaped by its relational context. Appel et al. (2018) argue that from an anthropological perspective, infrastructure is a terrain of power and contestation: controlling infrastructure means controlling the distribution of resources, people, and ideas. In 'The Promise of Infrastructure', the authors question who benefits from infrastructure and who must fight for essential services. Our analysis of housing infrastructures aligns with these debates, particularly regarding which relations necessitate a responsibility for Northern housing, and whose voices influence housing policy.

The absence of infrastructure, or the maintenance of them, bring neoliberal reconfigurations into the spotlight (Appel et al., 2018), redefining relationships and social norms (Schwenkel, 2015). Infrastructure studies thus serve as a conceptual tool for a critique of capitalism (Appel et al., 2018; Gansauer et al., 2025) by revealing relations between different stakeholders such as municipalities, companies, businesses, residents and services. The analysis of our empirical material shows how conventional housing market models do not suffice for housing provision in the Arctic. Instead, we draw on Larkin (2013), who highlights that infrastructures are significant not only for their material functions but also for what they symbolize about the future. Housing, in particular, reflects these aspirations as it profoundly affects people's everyday lives.

Similar to a human life-course, Gupta (2018, p. 62) explores the temporalities of infrastructure by focusing on the relations between futurity and ruination throughout their lifetimes. Such dynamics of future and ruin, desire and decay, are especially evident in our case studies illustrating the relocation of entire neighborhoods in Malmfälten, as well as the generally dire housing conditions in Nunavut. For Gupta (2018), infrastructure is not static but a shifting, decaying process sustained through repair. While we align with this view, we emphasize the importance of framing infrastructures as relational, shaped by interactions between humans, non-humans, and the built environment, with housing serving as one crucial component.

Infrastructure reflects broader inequalities – class, gender, race and kinship influence access to essentials like housing, water, and electricity (Appel et al., 2018; Ferguson, 2012). Settler colonial infrastructures have marginalized certain groups, relegating them to areas with inadequate services, while benefiting others (Spice, 2018). In place of such destructive developments, LaDuke and Cowen (2020) advocate for ‘alimentary infrastructure,’ in reference to infrastructure which is nurturing, sustaining, and regenerating in its intent, such as renewable energy projects, local food systems, and Indigenous-led economic alternatives. Unlike colonial infrastructures, focused on land development and profit, alimentary infrastructure fosters, grows and supports good relations. In our context, housing is an infrastructure which shapes relations reaching beyond the house’s inhabitants to reflect broader political, economic, and environmental conditions. By connecting the study of northern housing with an anthropological analysis of infrastructural relations, we highlight dependencies and desires between northern residents, and those who plan and build their homes.

Contextualizing the shift from iglus to apartments: case study regions and methods

Because of their stark differences in settlement patterns, infrastructure, governance structures, and demographic compositions, comparing the Malmfälten region and Nunavut offers a lens through which to examine how distinct northern contexts shape, and are shaped by, similar Arctic challenges. Their contrasts illuminate how varying colonial legacies, degrees of state involvement, and their different degrees of Indigenous populations, influence responses to shared issues such as housing. These communities can be seen as exemplary of many other Arctic communities that struggle with similar issues, and a comparative study allows for the articulation of underlying relations and causes of the housing crisis.

The comparative ethnographic approach (Abramson & Gong, 2020; Palmberger & Gingrich, 2013) for this work was guided by conversations within the ERC Advanced Grant project ‘Building Arctic Futures: Transport Infrastructures and Sustainable Northern Communities – InfraNorth’, which led us to realize how different the housing situations are in Malmfälten and Nunavut. Candea (2019) argues that comparison functions as a heuristic yet imperfect tool that produces valuable insights if used with awareness of its limitations. The comparative framework which we use for our analysis is structured around thematic analysis (Silverman, 2014). Through discussions, housing emerged as a key topic in the research of Arctic transport infrastructures in both case study regions. By employing a comparative lens set on a single topic across various field sites, we were able to examine differences and similarities not only across local contexts, but in the overarching structures which lead to housing shortages in each region.

Similar topics and terminology that appear in all cases were leading us to question the varying expressions of these housing crises in each region. If transportation infrastructure is not the determining factor in northern housing availability, what is? In Malmfälten, our case study regions are well connected to national and international transportation networks which enable swift transmission of goods, materials, and people, while Nunavut is not connected to any of the national infrastructure networks and must rely on annual shipments from Southern Canada to each community. Yet, in both regions, the housing crisis – understood as the lived experience of housing precarity – emerged as one of the most frequently discussed concerns among residents.

Our research builds on three ethnographic case studies conducted between February 2022 and December 2024. Schmid conducted fieldwork in five communities in the Qikiqtani region of Nunavut, which vary in population size and density: Iqaluit, Kimmirut, Pond Inlet, Resolute Bay, and Grise Fiord. Schmid's fieldwork stays included a six month stay and four additional short-term visits spanning between one to four months, during which she continued research and discussed her findings. In Nunavut, Schmid spoke with around 180 people during informal conversations documented in fieldnotes, and recorded 60 semi-structured interviews. Adams conducted fieldwork in the Malmfälten region, in the Swedish mining towns of Gällivare and Kiruna. These sites were visited seven times, with stays ranging from four days to two weeks. During this time, Adams engaged in 74 informal conversations, which are documented in the fieldnotes and eleven formal, semi-structured interviews were recorded.

Throughout our fieldwork, we took fieldnotes and supplemented them with photographs and videos, as well as additional notes capturing our observations and experiences. Interviewees included local politicians, administrators, hunters, and business owners, as well as a broad spectrum of residents differing in age, gender, socio-economic status, ethnicity, and nationality.

For the comparative thematic content analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Nowell et al., 2017), each researcher independently returned to their empirical material – transcripts and fieldnotes – to inductively develop five categories which were prominent in both regions: funding and governance, population dynamics, infrastructure and logistics, and suitability of housing in the North. These categories were then integrated with pre-existing analytical frameworks from previously examined materials. A collaborative process followed, where the combined categories were refined in relation to the research question and theoretical considerations.

Constructing scarcity: housing governance, funding, and relations

Nunavut, formerly part of the Northwest Territories, is Canada's youngest territory, located in the Eastern Canadian Arctic and home to a majority Inuit population. The territory is accessed by airplane or ship, as there are no roads connecting it to other parts of Canada. Currently, the territory's economy is dominated by administrative and resource extraction activities. Malmfälten, located in the far north of Sweden within the Arctic region of Norrbotten County, is a mining district shaped by some of Europe's largest iron ore deposits. The area includes towns such as Kiruna, Gällivare, and Malmberget, where communities have long been intertwined with large-scale extractive industries. Unlike other remote Arctic regions, Malmfälten is connected by road and rail to the rest of Sweden.

Although both regions face a housing crisis, its nature differs significantly. In Malmö, the crisis stems mostly from the mining industry's need to expand into residential zones, prompting the relocation of entire neighborhoods. As such, the lack of housing is a condition that is a consequence of industrial activity. In contrast, Nunavut's crisis is a result of inappropriate government policies and discrimination, resulting in an acute housing shortage, with too few homes to accommodate current and future populations. Severe housing shortages persist, leading to overcrowding with entire families share single rooms in Nunavut, while in Sweden, people often commute long distances or rely on fly-in fly-out arrangements before securing permanent housing often after being enrolled in waiting lists for several years. Although LKAB (2025) plays a major role in funding housing projects driven by mining expansion, urban planning remains the responsibility of municipalities, with elected governments tasked with developing long-term strategies to ensure these towns remain sustainable beyond the mining era (Malmgren et al., 2022). In this transformation process, involving local citizens in the relocation, design, and planning processes is a high priority, with municipalities emphasizing a participatory approach grounded in collaboration rather than top-down decision-making.

Funding and governance

When asked what infrastructural challenges her community faces, a woman from Kimmirut replied, 'One of the examples is units, or buildings: the ones that were built in the 1960s aren't being properly maintained. We're not given enough funding to take care of them.' Financing housing in the North is one of the most pressing challenges in both Sweden and Canada, and each country has attempted different solutions. A Swedish interlocutor emphasized the sheer lack of available housing: 'I think more people would be willing to move here, but they can't because there's nowhere to live at a reasonable price. And it's not only the price – it's just simply impossible to find anything.'

Nunavut's housing crisis is deeply marked by colonial and paternalistic attempts at directing Inuit lives without involving Inuit in the policy or decision-making; these dynamics continue to influence relations in the territory today. In Frobisher Bay, later renamed Iqaluit, in the 1960s, many Inuit built multi-room cabins out of improvised materials stemming from the town dump (Honigmann & Honigmann, 1965). While housing provisions have since changed, the policy of leaving Inuit to fend for themselves occurred throughout the territory during the 1940s-1960s. An interviewee who was forcibly relocated from Inukjuak to what is now Grise Fiord, explained to Schmid during a conversation in April 2023 how little support the federal government provided upon their arrival in 1953: 'We were to become reintroduced to our very own culture. To be self-reliant Eskimos once more. We were expected to have no assistance. No housing of any kind. We were to live off our own wit.' These scenes illustrate the Canadian policy of dispersal in place during the first decades of federal interest in the region, aimed at keeping Inuit in seasonal hunting lifestyles to sustain the fur trade. The government resisted providing housing, fearing that permanent dwellings would lead Inuit to abandon trapping and rely more on the state (Tester, 2006). Yet by this time, the fur trade had largely collapsed (Wenzel, 2017).

With increasing Qallunaat (non-Inuit) presence in the region came first attempts at housing policies, beginning with the 1959 rent-to-own scheme 'Eskimo Housing Loan Program', administered by the Department of Northern Affairs and Natural Resources

(Tester, 2009). Today's Nunavut Housing Corporation (NHC), is partly funded by the Canada Mortgage and Housing Corporation, the Government of Nunavut (GN) capital budget and the federal government National Housing Strategy. The majority of NHC's projects are related to public housing, however, the corporation also deals with houses on the market for purchase, house renovations, and repairs (Government of Canada, 2006; Nunavut Housing Corporation, 2024a).

A brief look into Swedish colonial history shows how in the early seventeenth century, authorities intensified colonial policies in Norrbotten, forcing Sámi to attend Swedish churches and schools. These actions were driven by a European mindset that perceived the Arctic as a blank slate, ready for the imposition of colonial, imperial, extractive and scientific agendas (Klinger et al., 2023). The existence of iron ore bodies in the region had been documented as early as the seventeenth century, with the first test mines being conducted in the eighteenth century. During this period, the Sámi and Tornedalians living in the area primarily utilized the land for hunting, fishing, cattle-based agriculture, and reindeer herding. In the early twentieth century, the first two decades of mining, LKAB did not employ Sámi and Tornedalians. After the First World War the mining company employed first Tornedalians, while Sámi were excluded until after the Second World War (Malmgren et al., 2022).

The completion of the railway linking Luleå, on the Gulf of Bothnia, and Narvik, on the Arctic Ocean, in 1902 facilitated efficient ore transport from both towns (Malmgren et al., 2022), but disrupted Sámi reindeer herding practices (Klinger et al., 2023; Malmgren et al., 2022). These problems persist until today, as various groups, ranging from tourism to Swedish Space Cooperation, and new mining operations, seek to establish a presence on the land.

With both public housing and various homeownership programs, Nunavut's NHC offers housing as a social good, largely independent of one's ability to pay, and as a market commodity, depending on which program residents are eligible for. Currently, the minimum rent in public housing is set at \$60/month with an annual income below \$33,280 (Nunavut Housing Corporation, 2024d). Writing in 2009, Frank Tester noted that 60% of the population was living in public housing, of which 98% were Inuit (Tester, 2009, p. 137). By 2021, 85.9% of tenant households in Nunavut resided in subsidized housing (Statistics Canada, 2022). Amidst this crisis, federal funding for social housing across Canada has steadily declined since the 1980s (Gaetz et al., 2014), leaving Nunavut with drastically increased construction costs, which reached \$670 per square foot in February 2024 (Beers, 2024). Although limited, today's federal funding flows through programs such as the Canadian Mortgage and Housing Corporation (CMHC), or the Canada Housing Infrastructure Fund. Further support in Nunavut is provided by the national Inuit association to Nunavut Tunngavik Incorporated (NTI), which is the legal representation of Inuit in the territory. As former Nunavut Senator Glenn Patterson noted in an interview, the various streams of funding complicate processes and lack transparency. Compiling this is the horizontal, multilevel, governance model practiced in Nunavut, where the GN is a public government responsible for all residents and NTI the legal representation for the majority, but not entirety, of the territorial population. These overlapping and at times conflicting governmental bodies work against each other as often as they work together, delaying policies and developments in a fog of jurisdictions (Rodon, 2014).

Allocation of Nunavut's public housing is dependent on one's standing in a territorial point-rating-system administered by the local housing associations. According to a report on the 2022–2023 bilateral agreement between CMHC and NHC, points are awarded according to factors such as the following: total time on the list, domestic violence, or separated families (CMHC-Nunavut, 2023). And yet, residents complain about not knowing what their ranking is. While sitting at a café in Iqaluit, one woman without housing explained that she has applied for a spot at the women's shelter for years but she still does not have enough points. She said she can accrue points by applying each time she receives income support, but in the meantime, she sleeps at the dam shelter.

Even after securing public housing, higher incomes can disqualify residents, forcing them out and discouraging job-seeking. Instead, people adapt to raise their chances of getting housing (Ikey, 2021), for example by having more children, as a young woman from Resolute Bay described:

To get a house you need to have, like, five kids, or you're practically homeless, so you can go on the list. But then it would take five years, or you would have to room with other people. Because there's only houses with, like, four, five rooms, three rooms. Never one or two.

The physical construction of homes therefor stands in direct relation to family sizes for many Nunavummiut. The homes themselves seldom have five or more bedrooms, yet the more children one has, the more likely one is to receive public housing. These examples clearly showcase how housing as an infrastructure has social effects extending beyond its walls to influence demographics, education, or employment.

While overcrowded family homes are not an issue and the stakes are significantly lower, similarly unreliable processes for attaining housing can also be found in Sweden. While the outcome may be similar, the housing crisis in Gällivare and Kiruna largely stems from recent urban transformation. Despite the presence of high-quality, newly built housing, demand continues to outpace supply, with waiting times ranging from anything between 18 months (for those with work contracts) to eight years, depending on the eligibility criteria for different queues. In Gällivare a resident spoke about three main housing cooperatives with waiting lists: HSB, Sweden's largest federation of cooperative housing; Topbostäder AB, a local housing company; and LKAB, which manages a separate queue for apartments they control. Despite efforts to expand the housing supply, demand still outpaces availability. LKAB has funded housing projects, but relocations of entire town sections, including the entire area of Malmberget in Gällivare and parts of the old city center in Kiruna, intensify shortages. A resident explained the challenges of the queue system:

I have a small apartment and joined the most popular queues for a larger apartment, but in order to stay in the queue, you need to log into the system at least once a year. I forgot and lost my spot. (...). There is no system within the queuing system to know what number you are in the current list, which is annoying.

While some wait for a spot in accommodation that has already been built, others wait for housing that has been planned but not completed. One of the most significant recent setbacks in Gällivare's construction is the stalled multicenter project in the city center. The municipality estimated the building costs, which were then covered by LKAB. However, prices have since gone up, and the project remains stagnant. Local residents express frustration, noting that the municipality lacks sufficient funds to proceed with construction. Despite efforts to find builders and secure offers, no progress has been made recently. A

local resident shared, ‘The entire project is on ice – nothing is happening. They don’t have the money to finish it.’

By uncovering Arctic residents’ relations to their housing systems and situating them within historical contexts, we demonstrate how current housing conditions are shaped by both industrial legacies (Sweden) and colonial bureaucracies (Canada). These forces influence not only the availability and accessibility of housing but also people’s choices to move. The way housing is funded and governed locally plays a crucial role in shaping residents’ well-being and the long-term sustainability of their communities.

Population dynamics

Nunavut has a population of about 39,000, 80% of whom identify as Inuit (Statistics Canada, 2022, p. 2024). Despite its vast geography, the territory’s 25 towns and hamlets are bursting at their seams. In the coming years, the current housing crisis is likely to worsen due to Nunavut’s exceptionally high birth rate: Canada’s national average is 1.33 births per female, while Nunavut’s is at 2.22, with the high fertility projection rising to 3.43 by 2048 (Government of Canada, 2024). Of Nunavut’s 9,925 private households, 33% live in overcrowded and unsuitable conditions (Statistics Canada, 2022), as opposed to 5.4% nationally (Government of Canada, 2022). Such extreme overcrowding expedites the spread of diseases – tuberculosis remains an active epidemic – and increases domestic violence, directly impacting primarily Inuit physical and mental health (Knotsch & Kinnon, 2011; Perreault et al., 2023).

In Sweden, overcrowding of individual buildings does not present as a problem. In Malmfälten, the demand for iron ore follows cyclical fluctuations, with booms and busts that directly impact local population dynamics. A notable example of this phenomenon is the steel crisis of the late 1970s, which had severe ramifications for Kiruna and Gällivare, resulting in significant population decline exceeding 10% in the 1980s (Malmgren et al., 2022, p. 232). This led to a housing surplus, forcing the community to maintain empty buildings at a cost. Declining tax revenues weakened municipal services, prompting further outmigration. In response, the municipality reduced the housing stock, sparking preservation efforts that saved culturally significant buildings (Avango et al., 2022). Today, surging world-wide steel demand has reversed the trend.

While Nunavut and Malmfälten are concentrating on upgrading houses and building new homes, the regions cannot provide the necessary skilled labor, requiring the majority of workers to be flown in from the South. Nunavut’s capacity issues stem partly from inadequate training opportunities within the territory: Former mayor of Iqaluit, Kenny Bell, noted at the Nunavut Trade Show in September 2022, the North has a ‘human deficit’, not just in construction workers, but also in government positions. Qallunaat employees generally stay around two years before returning South, creating a highly transitory atmosphere without continued investment. This delays progress on projects or policies, and makes finding people who are motivated to do good work with impact beyond the time they plan to live in Nunavut or Malmfälten challenging. There is an urgent need for adequate housing for workers, construction crews, and in the tourism sector, which in Sweden grew sixfold in winter and fourfold in summer between 2006 and 2016 (Klinger et al., 2023).

While in Nunavut there is next to no private rental market, in Sweden, the rental market is influenced by private landlords who, as one resident pointed out, ‘They can ask for basically whatever rent.’ In both towns, trades workers are often housed at the few existing

hotels, with average nightly prices of around 400 Canadian Dollars or 2500 SEK, adding significantly to construction costs. In the Swedish Arctic, such costs also pose a major obstacle to new housing development as one resident explained:

To build a similar house here and in the south – the price is about double. It's difficult to have labor here because it's really expensive to find housing for the construction workers. The hotel prices are so high, and there is simply no space to accommodate the workers. Also, housing companies think people live here just temporarily, and because the mine is emphasizing automation processes. They think that the housing demand wouldn't stay for a long time. LKAB should build more because they also need more living space for their own workers.

All over the Arctic, fly-in workers, along with permanent employees from the South, often receive employer-provided housing. The GN, one of the biggest employers in Nunavut, offers staff housing, but employees only receive GN housing if they do not already have housing in the community they work in. Most people who fall into this category come from the South, creating the impression for some Nunavummiut that staff housing is unfairly allocated. One interviewee lamented, 'They [Southerners] get a house, furniture, even a truck sometimes.' A resident of Resolute Bay further described the situation in her community:

There's a lot of people that come in for work. ... Cause like the military that comes in, the workers that come in for ATCO, for management jobs, like at the Hamlet, at the store. Just a lot of people that have to get flown in. And then they take housing.

Fly-in-fly-out workers pose an additional challenge for Swedish municipalities: while they may contribute to the local economy, they are not counted as permanent residents, leading to reduced tax revenues for the municipalities. A Kiruna resident shared their own calculations on what would best benefit the town:

If everyone working here also would live here, we could have around 30,000 residents, closer to the 32,000 we had in the late 1970s. Right now, we have about 22,000, and we would like to be around 25,000, but that depends on how things at LKAB go.

This statement was opposed by an LKAB employee who noted during an interview in 2022:

There is lots of talk in town that LKAB relies on fly in- fly out workers, but 95% of LKAB workers live where they work, we know it from their addresses. From the company's perspective it's important to have people here. Our goal is to have more houses here than when we started tearing down.

It should be noted that the suggested 95% reported in the interview refers to personnel directly employed by LKAB, and does not encompass all contractors or entrepreneurs engaged in the mining industry.

Examining population dynamics reveals housing's direct relationship to health, which can influence residents' educational opportunities and employability, impacting their income and capacity to make decisions about their own lives. Fly-in fly-out workers make the housing crisis visible by exposing the gap between labor demands and local housing capacity, revealing deeper strains on already limited infrastructure.

Infrastructure and logistics

Communities in Nunavut depend on annual sealift resupply by cargo ships, or expensive air freight deliveries for construction materials and machinery. Without any roads connecting hamlets, each of the 25 communities is dependent on their own local infrastructure with

minimal outside support. However, a new housing project announced by the GN in October 2022 aims to build 3000 homes across Nunavut by 2030. The project is to be completed in collaboration with Nunavut construction company, NCC Development, and the NHC. Yet skepticism around the ambitious project's funding and timeline is high among residents.

During a dinner with friends in Iqaluit, the feasibility of Nunavut3000 was discussed. When asked to rate their skepticism about the plan, one interlocutor chose 9.5 out of 10, arguing that the infrastructure is not yet available for them to build that many homes in the envisioned period of time. They continued, explaining that the lack of energy sources is a true hindrance to construction in Nunavut. Communities do not have enough energy available to power the machines and trucks needed to build so many structures at once. Everything runs off diesel, and they would have to transport all the building materials up to each community by sealift, which takes time and you can only fit so much on a cargo ship. The communities that only get one sealift a year cannot support a sudden drastic increase in sealift area taken up by construction when they need that space for food supply and other necessities. Trucks and other construction vehicles would need diesel or gas to run, and the more of them there are up in a community, the more diesel and gas they need. Compounding this challenge, each community only has tanks of certain sizes, which need to last until the next sealift. The dinner guests suggested it was likely that if Nunavut3000 actually wants to build 3000 homes by 2030, some of the communities will have to build second or third fuel tanks. This again takes construction: sealift, materials, space, and manpower.

In Sweden, once a project moves forward, efficient road, rail, and air networks ensure quick delivery and integration of materials. Once apartments are completed they fill rapidly. When housing shortages become critical, people tend to adopt creative solutions that, while initially intended to be short-term, can end up lasting much longer than planned. In Sweden's mining towns, temporary solutions like living in caravans at camp-sites are sometimes the only affordable and available option. A local bus driver told Adams that some people live in run-down cottages in remote areas outside the city, relying on private cars to commute long distances to work. Many of the buildings are in need of maintenance and repair, as one young Kiruna resident reflected:

'When things get cracky, it's not a big deal if it's something like this' (pointing to a column).
'But it's very bad when it's infrastructure like gas. The old high school had a huge problem. But all the experts said, 'No, it's fine, it's just below the danger level. There are a lot of cracks in buildings around the city ... you have to watch out for them! Haven't you seen them?'

Despite the challenges, mining investments have provided valuable infrastructure for the towns where one interlocutor described the company's contribution to the community.

Our comparison thus highlights the stark differences in the fundamental infrastructure and logistics required for delivering building supplies and operating essential machinery on construction sites, making it visible that the problem of Arctic housing shortages does not lie solely in the challenges of transporting materials to the regions.

Arctic climate and climate change

The harsh Arctic climate determines when construction can begin and when it must end for the season, directly impacting the pace and cost of development. Generally, construction in the Arctic region occurs in a flurry of activity over four or five months. In Malmfälten, the construction season typically spans from May to early November. This schedule is

influenced by the region's harsh winter conditions, which can make construction challenging or impossible during the colder months. Buildings are designed for Arctic conditions, yet construction and design failures still emerge at times, as seen in the case of the newly built Kiruna city hall:

This building isn't very popular with some people. If you look up, you can see white spots—mould. The architects are often from the South, they don't know how to build for the Arctic. There's mould everywhere. In spring, they put out buckets to catch the dripping water.

Although this perspective doesn't capture the full picture – many residents take pride in the new city hall – it highlights the challenges of building in Arctic climates. The hall was carefully planned with local engagement, incorporating elements from the old building, and now includes accessible spaces for community use. In Nunavut, construction seasons vary with latitude. In southern Baffin Island, construction may continue year-round, with exceptions during blizzards or extreme cold, while hamlets in the High North are often forced to pause between October and May. Climatic conditions also pose challenges for maintenance and repair of houses, with February as a notorious month of burst pipes and indoor floods in Nunavut, displacing residents for weeks to months before temperatures rise enough to fully repair the damage.

Nunavut's entire landmass is made of permafrost, which is now thawing due to global climate change, further challenging northern development. Permafrost requires specific construction techniques, such as drilling long steel poles through the active soil layer and into the frozen ground to stabilize the structure, or buildings raised on poles to avoid destabilization from flooding or erosion. Thawing permafrost limits land available for development, causes erosion, and even destabilizes current houses, which then require repair. Gartler et al. (2025) examine how infrastructure failure, mobility disruptions, and supply chain interruptions, among other factors are linked to permafrost thaw – insights that also apply to our Canadian examples. When a young man from Pond Inlet was asked what he would prioritize if he were given the chance to make decisions for his community, he responded,

I think it would be to focus more on adaptation. We drill giant metal rods to make sure that the permafrost melting won't affect the buildings in the long term. What if we can figure out a way to build a house on top of the land? Something that you can put on the land and it'll just maintain its stability while the permafrost, like, melts and stuff.

There are initiatives working on providing housing that is more adaptive to climate change conditions, such as cabins made out of sea cans in Pond Inlet, which sit on a gravel foundation and can be moved easily, but the majority of structures require deep stabilization and continue to use 'giant metal rods', skyrocketing the cost of their construction.

Our comparison underscores the need for Northern housing to be designed with full consideration of local climatic conditions, which continually shift and shape the very ground on which structures stand. At these latitudes, adapting construction and maintenance practices to rapidly changing environments is essential and citizen participation should be integrated at every stage of the building process, as residents possess deep, place-based knowledge and understand how to live with and adapt to the climate.

Building suitable houses

Building on the importance of local knowledge and climate-adapted practices, it becomes clear that simply increasing the number of homes in the Arctic is not enough. Sustainable

housing must also align with the specific needs and values of northern communities. Yet, what constitutes ‘suitability’ in housing varies: in Sweden, it often means well-located homes with pleasant views, well connected neighborhoods, and walkable streets, accessible services and recreation possibilities, while in Nunavut, it centers on availability, functionality, and cultural relevance. In Sweden, buildings are known to have excellent quality and are mostly well-adapted to Arctic conditions, supported by strong infrastructure and a state system which supports public-sector spending based on welfare systems. Community-engaged approaches that prioritize incorporating local residents’ voices into town planning are central to the planning process. Still, not all housing is considered suitable due to the emotional attachment to former homes that has not had time to grow in the new houses. While most residents in Kiruna and Gällivare acknowledge the necessity of the move due to the expansions of the mines, others struggle with the emotional impact of seeing the town they knew begin to disappear. An elderly female resident of Gällivare described, ‘I lived 16 years in a house from where we had to relocate. Three years ago, we got a compensation house from Boliden. For me, it was okay to move. I got a really nice new house.’

However, relocation experiences vary. An elderly resident spoke of the difficulty of leaving a home built by her father to move into a much smaller apartment who considers her home to be Malmberget. In Kiruna, one interlocutor reflected, ‘Of course, I would mind moving if I had to, but it’s necessary for the town to survive.’ Many who lived in the old town center, especially those with a long history in the area, feel the loss more keenly. For them, the view of the mine and the mountains from their homes was important. This sense of loss is even more palpable for those who are reluctant to fully embrace the changes. An elderly man claimed to have visited the new city center only three times: twice to vote, and once to check out the new shops. Some residents, like him, are resistant to the idea of moving, despite understanding its necessity: ‘In the new city, you can’t see anything. The buildings block your view of the mountains.’ The loss of the iconic buildings, especially those designed by Ralph Erskine (see for details Luciani & Poma, 2023), is deeply felt, with one resident describing the old town as ‘almost like a ghost town’ now, filled with fences and reminders of what once was. Another resident has decided to document the town’s transformation by taking pictures of changes and posting them on Facebook to share with friends and family.

In both Swedish towns, a program of preservation and relocation of historical buildings is being undertaken by LKAB, while others are being demolished and compensated for, either through payments or relocation. One long-time resident in Kiruna explained in 2023:

‘Tourists and people from outside sometimes ask about the lack of public protests regarding the relocations. But most of the people work for the mining companies. You wouldn’t fight your own employer. If we didn’t have these mining companies, the town would be much smaller. So we understand how important they are for the town.’

In Nunavut, suitability issues stem from housing decay, mold, and disrepair. Heavy maintenance is needed in such cases, but the skilled labor to conduct repairs is limited. The reliance on seasonal resupply further delays repairs, leaving many with broken windows to fight -40°C or more with the help of plastic garbage bags taped across window frames, for example. These compounded factors lead to the current reality: There are simply not enough buildings to house Nunavut’s residents. While housing development is accelerating through initiatives such as Nunavut3000, which help provide more

housing by constructing new buildings or renovating old ones, the buildings themselves are still largely built for Nunavummiut, but without taking their wishes into account. Such an approach is highly paternalistic and settler colonialist in its intent, constructing destructive styles of infrastructure in the long-term (LaDuke & Cowen, 2020).

Policies are beginning to change to reflect northern needs and desires, slowly shifting to becoming consent-based, alimentary, nurturing infrastructures. One example is Nunavut entrepreneur Alex Cook's project 'The Qammaq House', which integrates shipping containers to lower costs and reduce reliance on fly-in workers. Cook advocates for development plans that connect with local vocational trainees to build housing more sustainably. His blueprint of the Qammaq House supports local laborers while conceptualizing the home in a more culturally appropriate manner, attending to the ways Inuit have commonly used their homes (see [Government of Canada; Crown-Indigenous Relations and Northern Affairs Canada, 2019](#) for a discussion of culturally appropriate housing). Another example is the August 2024 reintroduction of the Nunavut Homeownership Assistance Program, led by the NHC, which offers 'residents who can afford the cost of owning and maintaining a home in Nunavut' a loan for construction materials (Nunavut Housing Corporation, 2024c). While this initiative still limits who is able to build their own home, successful residents will eventually leave the rental market, freeing up housing, and creating homes according to their own needs and desires in the process.

Discussion and conclusion

We illustrate key challenges of providing housing infrastructure by describing how climate, funding and governance, population dynamics, infrastructure and logistics, and housing suitability relate to housing development and maintenance in the North. The situations in Nunavut and Malmö differ drastically in regard to demographics, governance, funding schemes, and what (transport) infrastructure is available, yet both regions struggle to provide accommodation for their populations. The interrelations between our chosen categories of analysis demonstrate how northern housing scarcity is not determined by one single factor, but by how these factors interrelate in daily life.

Funding programs and governance styles heavily influence housing availability and suitability in our case studies. Tester (2006, p. 249) argues that housing in the North does not adhere to capitalist principles. He points out that some state actors hesitate to fund Inuit housing adequately, treating it as a market commodity instead of a social responsibility. This reluctance suggests that, within the welfare state, the universal logic of capitalist economies remains influential. The same could be applied to our Swedish case, where capitalist market economies are the obvious reason for a housing shortage. The Swedish model is a distinctive blend of market economics and state regulation, designed to balance social welfare with market-led economy. The welfare state known as 'folkhemmet' has influenced all sectors since the end of World War II, including housing (Sandström, 2023). While traditionally state-regulated, Sweden's rental housing market has been gradually deregulated since the 1990s to encourage competition. This shift has led to growing challenges such as segregation, rising rents, tenant displacement, and evictions (Sandström, 2023, p. 2).

As both case study regions show, it is highly risky to build in the Arctic from an economic perspective. There is a lack of incentive to invest due to the diminishing population in Swedish communities. In Nunavut, communities' populations are increasing rapidly, yet the absence of a housing market disincentivizes developers from investing. Our comparison

thus shows that housing is not directly tied to increases or decreases in population, but is determined by economic factors and a political unwillingness from central governments to undertake anything contrary to the market economy. Furthermore, this suggests that decision-makers fail to recognize housing as a relational infrastructure central to maintaining a mentally and physically healthy population, which could potentially increase market interest in the region.

In Sweden, the infrastructure and logistics to support construction processes are given, yet the towns of Gällivare and Kiruna are still dealing with a housing crisis. Housing, as a limited resource, is not directly connected to the availability of infrastructure – though it accelerates the building process once funding and human capacity are in place, lowering the overall cost by decreasing transportation costs and contracting times. The infrastructure housing development depends on, is at the whim of the Arctic climate, which can easily put important logistics routes out of commission for months, stalling projects and leaving people with homes in disrepair. As global climate change accelerates warming in the North, the housing industry is faced with the challenge of not only building enough new housing to accommodate the population, but to maintain or renovate older homes to avoid further destruction due to shifting land, or unpredictable waterways. The suitability of northern housing is as much dependent on population and climate as it is on adequate funding and governance. As such, housing infrastructures' relations are inextricably tied to the agenda of governing parties and the dreams of market economists.

In thinking of housing as an expression of infrastructural relations, we draw on Simpson (2017), who underlines the necessity of consent and mutual responsibility in maintaining good relations. Consent is based on the opportunity to make a free and informed decision prior to any project moving forward, which speaks for the necessity of more inclusive planning practices. This understanding of relations can also be applied to consultation efforts, funding schemes, and maintenance provisioning for northern housing. Without good relations, official systems fail, and when official systems fail, local social relations help to cushion the fall. As such, infrastructure failure is simultaneously a social failure. Here we do not mean a failure of the infrastructure itself when it works with its intended purpose, we are far more referring to infrastructure as a magnifying glass of the failure of the state to support certain groups and take these groups' and communities' needs seriously.

By framing infrastructure as a set of relations rather than simply a network of objects in our built environment, we have redirected infrastructure discourse to center on reciprocity and nurture, rather than extraction and dispossession. Following this understanding of infrastructure necessitates consent and Indigenous and local governance in infrastructural decision-making, especially when it comes to Arctic housing. Decolonizing processes of housing development are not just about resistance to, or rejection of, harmful projects, but about creating (alternative) housing options that reflect Northern values and needs.

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